

ELEMENTAL IMPURITIES IN PQRI TABLETS VIA EXHAUSTIVE EXTRACTION	COMPANY/LABORATORY INFORMATION: _____	PQRI EXHAUSTIVE EXTRACTION VERSION 1 PAGE 1 OF 7
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SCOPE AND PRINCIPLE

This procedure measures impurity levels of ICH Q3D Class 1 and 2A elements (As, Cd, Hg, Pb, Co, Ni, and V) in PQRI Interlab Study tablets. This is the method intended to be used by **ALL LABORATORIES** participating in the PQRI Interlaboratory Study.

Samples are acid-digested with nitric acid in a microwave digestion system. The resulting solutions are diluted, and then analyzed by inductively coupled plasma mass spectrometry (ICP-MS) using an external calibration curve and an internal standard specific to each analyte. Results are reported in ppm (µg/g).

GENERAL INSTRUCTIONS

This method has been generalized to accommodate a range of operating systems; users must ensure that they do not exceed any manufacturer-recommended specifications for their individual equipment.

In this method, “pipet” refers to the use of automatic pipettes. Where the method instructs to “add”, the volume can be dispensed by a bottle top dispenser or graduated cylinder.

SAFETY

Staff performing work should be appropriately qualified and trained to do so. Make sure to follow proper safety protocols. Proper PPE (i.e. gloves, lab coat, fume hood, etc.) and extreme caution must be used when working with concentrated acids.

REAGENTS

All standard solutions should be NIST traceable. It is generally preferable to utilize a second source for all analyte stock standards, however, for the purposes of this project, it is not required.

Reagent	Recommended Grade/Concentration	Supplier	Lot Number	Exp. Date
Deionized (DI) water	18MΩ		NA	NA
Nitric acid	Ultra-trace metal grade / 67-70%			
Nitric acid	Trace metal grade / 67-70%			
Hydrochloric acid	Ultra-trace metal grade / 32-35%			
Hydrochloric acid	Trace metal grade / 34-37%			
10 µg/mL Cd	NA			
10 µg/mL Pb	NA			
10 µg/mL As	NA			
10 µg/mL Hg	NA			
10 µg/mL Co	NA			
10 µg/mL V	NA			
10 µg/mL Ni	NA			
1,000 µg/mL Ga	NA			
1,000 µg/mL Rh	NA			
1,000 µg/mL Tl	NA			
1,000 µg/mL Au	NA			

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LABWARE/EQUIPMENT

Equivalent items to those listed below may be used, provided they contribute no additional metal contamination to the preparation or analysis process, and they are suitable for laboratory use. The 50 mL tubes are calibrated to meet Class A tolerance requirements (± 0.25 mL at all volume marks for 50 mL tubes) in accordance with ASTM E1272 Standard Specification for Laboratory Glass Graduated Cylinders. Polypropylene or Teflon volumetric flasks certified to Class A tolerance may be used in lieu of tubes.

Labware
Disposable plastic cups
Disposable plastic spatulas
Weighing paper
LDPE bottle; 4 L and 1 L
Graduated cylinder; plastic and/or glass; 250 mL
Graduated flat-bottom polypropylene (PP) tubes; 50 mL
Calibrated automatic pipette; 1-10 μ L
Calibrated automatic pipette; 10-100 μ L
Calibrated automatic pipette; 100-1000 μ L
Calibrated automatic pipette; 500-5000 μ L

Equipment/Apparatus
Microwave digestion system
Analytical Balance
ICP-MS; equipped with autosampler

LABWARE PREPARATION

- Labs should follow internal procedures for ensuring labware is clean and contaminant free prior to use.

REAGENT PREPARATION

- Cleaning solution preparation Labs should prepare all appropriate cleaning and rinse solutions for their instruments per internal procedures.

STANDARD PREPARATION

Note: Alternate sizes and types of containers (i.e., tubes) from what is listed in the following steps may be used. If an alternate container is utilized, ensure that it meets class A tolerances and adjust all necessary volumes to ensure concentrations remain the same as what is provided.

- Intermediate Standard Solution (125 ng/mL Cd, Pb, and V; 250 ng/mL Hg; 500 ng/mL As, Co, and Ni): Prefill a 50 mL tube with approximately 25 mL of DI water. Add 1 mL of ultra-trace HNO₃ and 1 mL of ultra-trace HCl to the tube. Pipet stock standard aliquots specified in the table below into the tube. Dilute the contents to 50 mL with DI water, cap the tube, and mix the solution well.

Stock Standard Aliquot (mL)						
10 ppm Cd	10 ppm Pb	10 ppm As	10 ppm Hg	10 ppm Co	10 ppm V	10 ppm Ni
0.625	0.625	2.5	1.25	2.5	0.625	2.5

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- Intermediate Internal Standard (IS) Solution (1000 ng/mL Ga, 500 ng/mL Rh, TI): Prefill a 50 mL tube with approximately 25 mL of DI water. Add 1 mL of ultra-trace HNO₃ and pipet 0.05 mL of the 1,000 µg/mL Ga stock standard, 0.025 mL of the 1,000 µg/mL Rh stock standard, and 0.025 mL of the 1,000 µg/mL TI stock standard into the tube. Dilute the contents to 50 mL with DI water, cap the tube, and mix the solution well.
- Calibration and QC Solutions: Prepare calibration standard solutions by filling 50 mL tube with approximately 20 mL of DI water. Add 1 mL of ultra-trace HNO₃, and 1 mL of ultra-trace HCl. Pipet 1 mL of intermediate internal standard solution and the appropriate aliquots of intermediate and stock standard solutions. Dilute to 50 mL with DI water, cap the tube, and mix well. Preparation details for typical standard levels are shown in the table below. A minimum of four calibration standards are needed.

Solution ID	Calibration/QC Standard Solution Concentration (µg/L)					Intermediate Standard (mL)	10 µg/mL V (mL)	10 µg/mL Ni (mL)
	Cd, Pb	As, Co	Hg	V	Ni			
Cal Blank / QC Blank	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Cal Standard 1	0.05	0.2	0.1	0.05	0.2	0.02	0	0
Cal Standard 2	0.25	1	0.5	0.25	1	0.1	0	0
Cal Standard 3/ QC Standard	1	4	2	1	4	0.4	0	0
Cal Standard 4	5	20	10	5	20	2	0	0
Cal Standard 5	0	0	0	20	40	0	0.1	0.2

SAMPLE PREPARATION

- Place one tablet between two sheets of weighing paper and break into smaller pieces with mortar and pestle.
- Weigh entire crushed tablet into a clean microwave vessel. Record the weight to the nearest 0.001 g in the table below and on the Reporting spreadsheet. Prepare triplicate samples of each sample tablet concentration level, Tablet Level 1, Tablet Level 2, and Tablet Level 3 in the same manner.

Sample ID	Replicate Digested Mass (g)
Tablet Level 1	1 –
	2 –
	3 –
Tablet Level 2	1 –
	2 –
	3 –
Tablet Level 3	1 –
	2 –
	3 –

- Method Blank: Follow the procedure for the sample preparation except no sample is added to the vial/vessel. Prepare a total of three method blank samples.
- Raw Material Analysis (selected labs): If raw materials are to be analyzed alongside tablet samples, weigh out approximately the following masses of each raw material in triplicate into clean microwave vessels.

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Material	Target Mass (g)	Replicate Digested Mass (g)
Microcrystalline Cellulose	0.150	1 – 2 – 3 –
Magnesium Aluminum Silicate Clay (Veegum)	0.025	1 – 2 – 3 –
Lactose	0.1325	1 – 2 – 3 –
Pregelatinized Starch	0.05	1 – 2 – 3 –
Stearic Acid	0.150	1 – 2 – 3 –
Ferric Oxide Red	0.0125	1 – 2 – 3 –
Silicon Dioxide, As Co Hg	0.01125	1 – 2 – 3 –
Silicon Dioxide, Cd Pb Ni	0.010	1 – 2 – 3 –

Record the weight to the nearest 0.001 g in the "Replicate Digested Mass" column and on the Reporting spreadsheet.

- Pipet 10 mL of HNO₃ and 50 µL of 1,000 µg/mL Au (for Hg stabilization) into each vial/vessel. Reagents must be added in a manner so the walls of the vial/vessel could be rinsed down. Depending on the minimum operational volume of the microwave and vessels, it may be necessary to add deionized water to achieve the appropriate final digestion volume.
- Cap each vial/vessel.
- Assemble the digestion vessels and place into the microwave.
- Microwave digestion method: Use an appropriate power level for the microwave or vessel so as not to exceed safe operational parameters. Follow the below general program design and record power level:
 - 1) Ramp to 175 °C for 10 min.
 - 2) Hold at 175 °C for 10 min.
 - 3) Allow solutions to cool to <60 °C.
- Once samples have cooled, remove rack/vessels from microwave system.

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- Intermediate Solution Preparation: Transfer the solution from the vial/vessel into a 50 mL tube. Rinse the cap and vial/vessel with a few milliliters of DI water and add the rinsate to the 50 mL tube. Repeat the rinsing of the vial/vessel two more times. Dilute solution in the tube to 50 mL with DI water. Cap and mix well.
- Test Solution Preparation: Pipet 1.0 mL of the sample intermediate solution into a 50 mL tube. Add 0.8 mL of Ultra-trace HNO₃ and 1 mL of Ultra-trace HCl. Pipette 1 mL of intermediate IS solution into the tube. Dilute to 50 mL mark with DI water. Cap and mix well.

Comments/Observations/Deviations:

INSTRUMENT OPERATION

Example detection schemes for each analyte are given below. The internal standard and CCT gas used to report data should be documented along with the data. Please note: additional isotopes may be monitored alongside the required isotopes, but only results for the specified isotopes will be considered as part of the formal data analysis.

Analyte	Isotope	Example IS element	Example Analysis mode/add gas
V	51	Rh 103*	NH ₃
Co	59	Rh 103*	He
Ni	60	Rh 103*	He
As	75	Rh 103*	He
Cd	111	Rh 103	Standard
Hg	202	TI 205	Standard
Pb	Sum of 206+207+208 [†]	TI 205	Standard

*Rh was used during method development, but alternate elements may be used per standard lab practices.

[†] Summed through correction equation

ANALYSIS

- Warm up and optimize the instrument according to the manufacturer's guidelines. Perform any applicable time-of-use performance checks.
- Prepare sufficient rinse solution (2% HNO₃, and 2% HCl) so that the sample introduction system can be rinsed between the analysis of each blank, standard, or test solution. It is also recommended to condition the

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<p>sample introduction system for 10-15 min with rinse solution prior to analysis and include 1-3 blank solutions to establish a stable baseline before starting the actual calibration.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> <input type="checkbox"/> Analyze the calibration blank and calibration standard solutions, preferably in order of ascending concentration. Build a linear (non-weighted) regression plot for each analyte using the instrument software. <input type="checkbox"/> Analyze the QC Blank solution. <input type="checkbox"/> Analyze the QC standard followed by the QC Blank. Repeat analysis of these two solutions after at least every 10 sample test solutions. <input type="checkbox"/> Dispense the “Liquid Standard” sample directly from its container into an acid-washed and dried sample tube and analyze without additional dilution. <input type="checkbox"/> Analyze the method blank(s). <input type="checkbox"/> Analyze the sample test solutions. If sample test solution concentration exceeds the maximum concentration of the highest standard, verify if measured analyte intensity of the analyte in test solution exceeds the measured analyte intensity in the highest standard. If necessary, either dilute sample to be within the calibration range or extend the calibration range by analyzing an additional standard at a higher concentration. <input type="checkbox"/> Analyze the QC standard followed by the QC Blank at the end of the sequence to verify instrument performance. 		
<p>QUALITY CONTROL REQUIREMENTS</p>		
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> <input type="checkbox"/> The correlation coefficient (r) must be ≥ 0.999 for each calibration curve. <input type="checkbox"/> The accuracy (%RE) of the calibration standards must be ≤ 20% for the lowest standard, and ≤ 10% for all other calibration standards. If the %RE is not within the limits, the source of poor accuracy must be identified and the calibration standards rerun. <input type="checkbox"/> The QC standard must be within 80-120% of the expected value for all elements. If the QC standard is not within limits, then the source of failure must be identified and corrective action taken, which may include preparation of a new set of standards, re-optimization, and/or recalibration of the instrument. <input type="checkbox"/> The measured value for the QC Blank must not exceed the value of the lowest standard. Failed QC Blank results may indicate carryover or contamination and would require appropriate corrective actions, such as increased rinse time between test solutions or system maintenance. Pass/fail of this criterion may influence the need to exclude a low standard and change the LOQ value. 		
<p>CALCULATIONS</p>		
<p><u>Equation 1: Calibration and QC Standards:</u></p>		
$\text{Std Test Soln Conc } \left(\frac{\mu\text{g}}{\text{L}} \right) = \frac{\text{Stock Std Certified Conc } \left(\frac{\mu\text{g}}{\text{mL}} \right) * \text{Stock Std Aliquot (mL)} * 1000 \left(\frac{\text{mL}}{\text{L}} \right)}{\text{Final Volume (mL)}}$		
<p><u>Equation 2: Sample Concentration:</u></p>		
$\text{Sample Conc } \left(\frac{\mu\text{g}}{\text{g}} \right) = \frac{\text{Analyte Test Soln Conc } \left(\frac{\mu\text{g}}{\text{L}} \right) * \text{Test Soln Vol (mL)} * \text{Intermediate Soln Vol (mL)}}{\text{Sample Weight (g)} * \text{Intermediate Soln Aliquot Vol (mL)} * 1000 \left(\frac{\text{mL}}{\text{L}} \right)}$		

Equation 3: Relative Error:

$$\% \text{ Relative Error (\%RE)} = \left[\frac{\text{Found Concentration} - \text{Nominal Concentration}}{\text{Nominal Concentration}} \right] * 100$$

RESULTS

By means of the instrument software and/or other calculation tools, determine each analyte concentration in the sample test solution and then calculate sample concentration using Equation 2 in the Calculations section. In the instrument software, a ratio of the analyte intensity to the IS intensity is calculated for each solution. These intensity ratios are plotted versus concentration for each analyte and a linear regression is determined. Slope, y-intercept, and correlation coefficient for the standard data is calculated. In the event of suspected solution contamination, a standard can be excluded from the regression calculation. A minimum of 4 calibration standards must be used to build a calibration curve.

Report each analyte sample concentration result in units of µg/g or ppm, using three significant figures. The default LOQ for each element (shown in the table below) is based on the calibration standard 1, and nominal sample weight 0.25 g.

Report results less than LOQ as "< [LOQ value] ppm"

Element	Cd	Pb	V	As	Co	Ni	Hg
LOQ (ppm or µg/g)	0.50	0.50	0.50	2.0	2.0	2.0	1.0